

**LEVEL OF SELF-EFFICACY OF PUBLIC SECONDARY SOCIAL SCIENCE
TEACHERS IN FOSTERING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: A BASIS FOR
DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM**

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Level of Self-Efficacy of Public Secondary Social Science Teachers in Fostering Inclusive Education: A Basis for Development Program

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the level of self-efficacy of Public Secondary Social Science Teachers in the three selected schools of District V in Quezon City in formulating a basis for a development program for teachers to foster inclusive education. Likewise, the teachers' profiles were also examined as part of the investigation. To achieve this goal, the researcher conducted a study to determine the level of self-efficacy in terms of inclusive instruction, collaboration, and managing behavior among public secondary social science teachers in the three selected public schools of District V in Quezon City. In this manner, the explanatory sequential mixed method was used to measure the teachers' degrees of self efficacy. The researcher also identified the concerns encountered by the public secondary social science teachers in terms of resources, difficulties, appropriateness, and workload. A qualitative design was also utilized to identify the challenges encountered by the respondents. A total of eighty-four (84) social science teachers currently employed in the three selected public secondary schools in District V of Quezon City were involved in this study using purposive sampling. Furthermore, data for the study were collected using two tools: the adapted Teacher Efficacy for Inclusive Practice (TEIP) scale, developed by Sharma et al. (2014), to assess teacher self-efficacy in inclusive education, and an adapted and standardized survey questionnaire, the Concerns about Inclusive Education Scale – Short Form (CIES-SF), also designed by Sharma et al. (2022), to explore challenges faced by teachers during the qualitative phase. The results revealed that the level of self-efficacy among public secondary social science teachers is high self-efficacy. The result on the significant difference in their level of self-efficacy against the profile variables of teachers revealed no significant difference. Ultimately, a basis for a development program in fostering inclusive education in the classroom was proposed to improve their level of self efficacy in addressing the challenges encountered by public secondary social science teachers.

Keywords: *efficacy, teachers, program, develop, education*

Introduction

As stipulated in Article XIV, section 1 of the 1987 constitution, the state shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels. All learners are expected to have access to all privileges in schools. Moreover, Sarı, Gökdağ, and Aslan Bağcı (2019) highlighted the importance of promoting inclusive education and changing negative attitudes towards diversity. It could be inferred that fostering inclusive education also poses a challenge that needs to be addressed.

UNESCO (2023) also stressed that inclusive education works to identify all barriers to education. This only means that it acknowledges the presence of the different concerns that emerge while fostering inclusive education. In the Philippines, the Department of Education recently released DepEd Order No. 23 s.2022 articulating that learners with diverse learning needs are identified, located, and evaluated to facilitate their inclusion in the general basic education school system. This aims to remove the barriers that impede the process of fostering inclusive education in schools.

Globally, implementing inclusive education in schools has been given importance by governments. In Canada, Tutton (January 28, 2020) reported that there is anecdotal evidence of improvements for students with learning disabilities and other concerns as the government implemented its five-year inclusive education program. In the U.S, its Education Department is planning to update federal mandates for how schools and colleges must accommodate students with disabilities (Munoz, May 10, 2022).

In the Philippines, Paunan (2023) reported that the government must commit to fully and effectively implementing the law on inclusive education for learners with disabilities as mentioned by Senator Win Gatchalian during the 18th Congress. Further, Gita-Carlos (2022) also reported that Former President Rodrigo Roa Duterte has signed a law mandating all schools nationwide to ensure inclusive education for learners with disabilities. Thus, this only shows that governments around the world are slowly becoming more aware of the importance of inclusive education.

In the study of Llego (2022), he mentioned that teachers should be the primary implementers of inclusive education. In order to be successful in fostering inclusive education, teachers' self-efficacy must be adequate.

Meanwhile, it is true that schools worldwide are exhausting all efforts to foster inclusive education, it is also a must to consider its implementation in each of the subject areas such as in social sciences. Moreover, one of the contexts of Social Science is to make people understand diversity and acceptance in society (Main et al., n.d). Fostering inclusive education in social sciences also proves to be essential because it allows the social science teachers to increase their full potential in implementing inclusive education in the classroom.

For the social science teachers to assess their performance in implementing inclusive education, it is proper to also assess their level of self-efficacy. According to Bandura as cited by Lopez-Garrido (2023), self-efficacy is defined as people's belief in their ability to control their functioning and events that affect their lives. With this, the teachers can become more confident in fostering inclusive education.

On one hand, according to Zimmerman and Cleary, as cited by Dullas (2018), the level of self-efficacy refers to its dependence on the difficulty level of a particular task. In other words, the level of self-efficacy of social science teachers depends on how difficult it is to implement inclusive education.

On the other hand, Bayram and Öztürk (2021) conducted a study among social science teachers where they found out that further interventions to increase teachers' awareness and knowledge about the philosophy and values of inclusive education, in general, was revealed.

This implies that social science teachers still need to raise awareness and knowledge about inclusive education. In addition, Kokare and Nimante (2022), stated that the complexity of an inclusive classroom requires teachers to have diverse competencies. It only proves that social science teachers should focus more on continuing professional development to address this issue.

To sum up, this study aims to identify the level of self-efficacy of public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education in terms of: 1) inclusive instruction; 2) collaboration; and 3) managing behavior. This is to help the teachers of social sciences evaluate themselves on how well they implement inclusive education in their classrooms. The researcher also aims to find out if there is a significant difference between the level of self-efficacy and their corresponding profile variables namely: 1) grade level handled; 2) teaching position; and 3) years in service.

Another goal of this study is to identify the concerns encountered by the public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education in the classrooms. This would help the teachers to address these concerns and help them develop solutions.

Furthermore, this study aims to help schools develop a program catering to inclusive education. For example, seminars and training will be organized to address the concerns in fostering inclusive education. Hence, this study will be beneficial to the public secondary social science teachers as they become aware of their level of self-efficacy. They will also be able to be more confident in fostering inclusive education in their classrooms.

Moreover, the students of these public secondary social science teachers will also be able to enjoy their classroom experiences as the teachers ensure that every learner matters. All students will be able to gain equal access to learning.

In addition, this study is also beneficial to the schools as they also become aware of the importance of fostering inclusive education in social science classrooms. Schools can even organize activities about social sciences where every teacher and learner can participate and share their skills and talents. For example, during the United Nations' Week, all students are welcome to join and represent the nation of their choice.

Finally, the Schools Division of Quezon City will also benefit from this study as they share the results of this study with all the other schools within each district. In a bigger perspective, the more schools to acknowledge the results of this research study only mean that more students, teachers, and other school personnel will be able to enjoy their school experiences.

Research Questions

The main purpose of the study is to determine the level of self-efficacy of public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education. Specifically, the researcher aims to answer the following questions:

Quantitative Analysis

1. What is the profile of the public secondary social science teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. grade level handled;
 - 1.2. teaching position; and
 - 1.3. years in service?
2. What is the level of self-efficacy of public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education in terms of:
 - 2.1. inclusive instruction
 - 2.2. collaboration; and
 - 2.3. managing behavior?
3. Is there a significant difference between the level of self-efficacy of public secondary social science teachers across profile variables as to grade level handled, teaching position, and years in service?
4. What are the concerns encountered by the public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education in terms of:
 - 4.1. Resources
 - 4.2. Difficulties
 - 4.3. Appropriateness; and

4.4. Workload?

5. Based on the findings of the study, what program may be proposed to the public secondary social science teachers to address the concerns encountered in fostering inclusive education?

Qualitative Analysis

Probing Question:

1. What are the challenges of the key informants encountered in fostering inclusive education?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used a systematic integration of both quantitative and qualitative data in a single study. In view of Santos (2021), this methodology is popularly known as the explanatory sequential mixed methods (ESMM). This approach was used to follow up the quantitative results with qualitative data. The qualitative data was used in the subsequent interpretation and clarification of the result for the quantitative data analysis. Additionally, a quantitative design was employed to underscore key aspects, while a qualitative approach was utilized in explanatory methodologies. This research design was appropriate because the researcher determined the level of self-efficacy of public social science teachers in fostering inclusive education: A basis for development program.

This will be followed by a quantitative data collection wherein the data to be collected are based on the level of self-efficacy of public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education and also the concerns encountered by the public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education. The researcher also adopted a standard and pilot-tested survey questionnaire from Sharma et. al (2022). The new sets of data will help in determining the problems in this study. This approach is used so that the quantitative data and results will provide a general picture of the research problem.

In this research, an adopted survey questionnaire from Sharma et. al (2022) has been the central tool to be used to gather data that are vital for the accomplishment of the study. This method will be used because its tailor fits the purpose of the study which is to determine the level of self-efficacy of public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education. Interviews were conducted with the five key informants to verify and confirm the result of the quantitative analysis. The quantitative and qualitative analysis results were integrated to identify the key priority areas that served as the basis for writing the proposed basis for the development program.

Respondents

In this academic endeavor, the researcher utilized all eighty-four (84) public secondary social science teachers who were teaching at the three selected schools in District V of the Schools Division of Quezon City. Throughout the conduct of the study, all eighty-four (84) participants cooperated and participated in the study.

The researcher aimed to include all public secondary social science teachers from the three selected schools in District V of Quezon City as participants in the study. Data obtained from the non-teaching staff of the selected schools indicated that there was a total of eighty-four (84) public secondary social science teachers for the academic year 2023- 2024. Furthermore, all respondents participated in the study conducted.

The qualitative phase of the research involved purposeful sampling, which implies the intentional selection of key informants to understand the central phenomenon, such as the challenges encountered by public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education. The idea is to select key informants who can provide the best answers to the research questions and who are considered "information-rich" individuals. From the five (5) individuals capable of offering accurate information on the challenges and concerns in fostering inclusive education within the three selected schools. The nature of the explanatory sequential mixed methods design involves two important components:

Quantitative (QUAN) and Qualitative (QUAL). The QUAL phase depends on the results from the first QUAN phase. This allowed the researcher to present multiple perspectives of the key informants to "represent the complexity of our world" (Creswell & Creswell, 2017) in fostering inclusive education in the social science classroom.

Instrument

To collect data that is vital to the study, the survey questionnaires will have three distinctive parts. The first part will focus on the demographic profile of the respondents, and the second part will determine the level of self-efficacy of public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education in social science. Finally, the third part will aim to identify the concerns encountered by the respondents in fostering inclusive education.

To measure the level of self-efficacy of public secondary social science teachers that foster inclusive education in social science, the researcher utilized an adopted survey questionnaire to attain the necessary data needed for the study. The research instrument to be utilized is a modified Teacher Efficacy for Inclusive Practice (TEIP) scale which is designed for teacher self-efficacy in the context of inclusive education created by (Sharma, Loreman and Forlin, 2014). In line with this, the survey questionnaires are composed of 18

questions which are divided into three parts: (1) efficacy in using inclusive instruction (EII), (2) efficacy in collaboration (EC), and (3) efficacy in managing behavior (EMB) which shows high internal consistency of Cronbach's Alpha of .89. This implies that the validity and reliability of the instrument which will be used to the study has been pilot tested to the sample with the same characteristics as the expected actual respondents of the study.

The third part of the survey questionnaire was also adopted from Sharman et.al (2022) with his four-point Likert scale entitled Concerns about Inclusive Education Scale – Short Form (CIES-SF). Moreover, the (CIES-SF) is composed of 12 questions that have been pilot-tested. This will be utilized to determine the concerns encountered by the public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education.

Procedure

To formalize the conduct of the survey in the selected schools, the use of the name of the school and the data to be derived from the survey, a formal letter of communication was sent to the school's division of Quezon City to seek their permission and approval. A copy of the letter with the signed approval and school stamp.

Quantitative Data Collection

The modified Teacher Efficacy for Inclusive Practice (TEIP) scale which is designed for teacher self-efficacy in the context of inclusive education created by (Sharma, Loreman and Forlin), which was turned into a paper and pencil survey, was sent out to all the public social science teachers to get their self-evaluation on the level of their self- efficacy in fostering inclusive education. The third part of the survey questionnaire was also adopted from Sharman et.al (2022) with his four-point Likert scale entitled Concerns about Inclusive Education Scale – Short Form (CIES-SF). Moreover, the (CIES-SF) is composed of 12 questions that have been pilot-tested. This scale was used to determine the concerns encountered by the public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education. The survey questionnaire was sent to their school and was created to allow the participants to be answered only for a week. An introductory message was added at the beginning of the survey form to inform the respondents of the purpose of the survey and that the survey was anonymous. Since the conducted study was face-to-face the researcher used it to organize the data for further exploration, analysis, and interpretation with the assistance of our school statistician.

Qualitative Data Collection

The second part of this research is the qualitative phase which focuses on explaining and supporting the result of the analysis that was made on data that has been gathered in the first part, the quantitative phase. The case studies design was used for collecting and analyzing the qualitative data.

A case study is a form of investigation that delves into a "bounded system" by extensively collecting detailed data from various sources, providing a rich contextual understanding (Priya, 2021). The purpose is to highlight the challenges encountered by the public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education.

The main approach involved conducting thorough semi-structured interviews either via telephone, face-to-face or through social media with five (5) key informants. These informants were provided with information beforehand about the interview schedule and were notified that the interview would be recorded and transcribed verbatim.

The steps in qualitative analysis include: (1) preliminary exploration of the data by reading through the transcripts and writing important data. This refers to the identification of the meaning units, (2) coding of data by segmenting and labeling the text. This refers to the identification of the condensed meaning units, (3) using codes to develop themes by aggregating similar codes together. This refers to the identification of the sub-themes, (4) connecting and interrelating themes, and (5) constructing a narrative.

Data Analysis

The results of the survey were tabulated and analyzed. The responses sheet was tallied manually, and it was summarized in SPSS using frequency distribution and weighted mean which determined the level of self-efficacy of public secondary social science teachers across their profile variable. Data summary per indicators was encoded in SPSS to find out whether significant differences in the responses exist between the level of self-efficacy across their profile variable using a one-way ANOVA. The test of significant differences helped decide whether there was a need to develop a proposed program.

The researcher also used a survey questionnaire about the concerns encountered by public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education. The responses of the respondents were analyzed and tabulated using the frequency distribution and weighted mean. The results of the survey have proven the concerns encountered by public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education.

For another layer of the study, the researcher conducted semi-structured interviews with the final five (5) key informants of the study to explore the challenges encountered in fostering inclusive education. Through the semi-structured interview process, the key informants' responses were analyzed and interpreted using Colaizzi's method. Furthermore, the data summary from the concerns encountered by the public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education and the responses of the key informants

from the semi-structured interview served as the basis for crafting the development program to foster inclusive education in the social science classroom.

Ethical Considerations

The survey sent to staff included a disclaimer stating that it was anonymous and did not record the identity of the respondents in any manner. For the respondents and research locale, a letter was sent to the Schools Division Office of Quezon City seeking permission to conduct the study in the three (3) selected schools in District V of Quezon City. Permission has been granted, and a copy of the signed approval. Additionally, an email was written to Mr. Sharma, the primary author of the Teacher Efficacy for Inclusive Practices (TEIP) scale and Concerns for Inclusive Education Scale – Short Form (CIES-SF) instruments, seeking permission to use and adopt the standardized original copy of the survey questionnaire. The key informants were asked to sign a consent form before the conduct of the interview. This was done to ensure that they voluntarily agreed to participate in the interview, to allow audio recording of the interview, and to permit transcription of the data for use in this study.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data collected in the study. In addressing the sequential explanatory mixed methods design, data analysis was done in two phases linked sequentially to the quantitative and qualitative phases of data collection.

Quantitative Phase

For clarity of presentation and consistency in the discussion, the data are presented following the order and sequence of the questions raised in Chapter 1, to wit: (1) the profile of the respondents in terms of their grade level handled, teaching position, and years in service (2) the description of the level of self-efficacy of public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education in terms of the Teacher Efficacy for Inclusive Practices (TEIP) scale, (3) the result of the test of significance (ANOVA) to determine if there is a significant difference across the profile variable of the respondents (4) the concerned encountered by the public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education in terms of the about Concerns Inclusive Education Scale – Short Form (CIES-SF).

1. Profile of the Public Secondary Social Science Teachers

The inclusion of the respondents' profiles in the study was motivated by the researcher's desire to make an informed decision regarding the suitability of a development program. This involved establishing a connection between the respondents' profiles and the study's hypothesis.

Grade Level Handled

Based on the data presented in Table 1, the profile of public secondary social science teachers across all grade levels in junior and senior high schools is depicted. It also illustrates the distribution of grade levels handled by faculty members of social sciences as follows: Grade 7 (15.48%), Grade 8 (11.90%), Grade 9 (23.81%), Grade 10 (17.86%), Grade 11 (15.48%), and Grade 12 (15.48%).

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in Terms of Grade Level Handled*

Nomenclature	Frequency	Percentage
Grade 7	13	15.48%
Grade 8	10	11.90%
Grade 9	20	23.81%
Grade 10	15	17.86%
Grade 11	13	15.48%
Grade 12	13	15.48%
Total	84	100.00%

Teaching Position

Table 2 presents the teaching positions of the faculty of the social science department. It also shows the frequency and percentage as follows: Teacher I (41.67%), Teacher II (17.86%), Teacher III (29.76%), Master Teacher I (5.95%), and Master Teacher II (4.76%).

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in Terms of Teaching Position*

Nomenclature	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher I	35	41.67%
Teacher II	15	17.86%
Teacher III	25	29.76%
Master Teacher I	5	5.95%
Master Teacher II	4	4.76%
Total	84	100.00%

Years in Service

Table 3 shows the profile of 84 public social science teacher respondents in terms of years in service. Out of the total population, 26 teachers have five (5) years of teaching experience with the highest percentage of 30.95%. In comparison, seven (7) teachers have already gained about 16 to 20 years of teaching experience with the lowest percentage of 8.33%. It can be noted that a large number of public secondary social science teachers are in the early stages of their teaching careers.

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in Terms of Teaching Position*

Nomenclature	Frequency	Percentage
5 years below	26	30.95%
6- 10 years	23	27.38%
11-15 years	10	11.90%
16-20 years	7	8.33%
21 years and above	18	21.43%
Total	84	100.00%

The Level of Self-Efficacy of Public Secondary Social Science Teachers in Fostering Inclusive Education

To evaluate the level of self- efficacy of public secondary social science teachers in the three selected schools. The table presents the level of self-efficacy of public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education in terms of inclusive instruction, collaboration; and managing behavior.

Inclusive Instruction

Table 4 indicates that the respondents obtained a mean of 3.60, implying that the teachers have high self-efficacy in terms of inclusive instruction. It also proves that teachers can effectively manage the tasks, responsibilities, and difficulties associated with their professional work, significantly impacting crucial academic results (such as students' achievement and motivation) and overall well-being in the workplace.

Moreover, they are more adept at taking risks and initiating higher expectations in their classes, leading to improved student accomplishment (Alibakhshi et al., 2020).

Table 4. *Mean Rating of the Respondents on the Level of Public Secondary Social Science Teachers in terms of Inclusive Instruction*

Nomenclature	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Level of Self-efficacy
I can use a variety of assessment strategies (for example portfolio assessment, modified test, performance-based assesment etc.	3.63	0.60	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy
I am able to provide an alternate explanation or example when students are confused	3.74	0.54	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy
I am confident in designing learning tasks so that the individual needs of students with diverse learning styles are accommodated	3.61	0.62	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy
I can accurately gauge student comprehension of what I have taught	3.50	0.65	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy
I can provide appropriate concerns for very capable students	3.63	0.62	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy
I am confident in adapting school-wide or state-wide assessments so that students with all diverse learning needs can be assessed	3.51	0.67	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy
Weighted Mean	3.60	0.62	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy

Collaboration

Table 5 presents that the respondents obtained a mean of 3.46, implying that the teachers have high self-efficacy in terms of collaboration. Therefore, teachers possess the capability to engage in group participation with diverse students effectively, demonstrating confidence and a positive mindset.

Furthermore, based on the study of Zee and Koomen (2016) teachers frequently use differentiated instruction and adjust goals to cater to students with different needs. This only proves that differentiated instruction is an effective strategy to let the students come up with a positive output despite their differences.

Table 5. Mean Rating of the Respondents on the Level of Public Secondary Social Science Teachers in terms of Collaboration

Nomenclature	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Level of Self-efficacy
I can assist families in helping their children do well in school	3.40	0.60	Agree	High Self-efficacy
I am able to work jointly with other professionals and staff (e.g., aides, other teachers) to teach students with diverse learning needs in the classroom	3.54	0.65	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy
I am confident in my ability to get parents involved in school activities of their children with diverse learning needs	3.42	0.59	Agree	High Self-efficacy
I can make parents feel comfortable coming to school	3.52	0.63	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy
I can collaborate with other professionals (e.g., itinerant teachers or speech pathologist) in designing educational plans for students with diverse learning needs	3.43	0.61	Agree	High Self-efficacy
I am confident in informing others who know little about laws and policies relating to the inclusion of students with diverse learning methods	3.43	0.66	Agree	High Self-efficacy
Weighted Mean	3.46	0.62	Agree	High Self-efficacy

Managing Behavior

Table 6. Mean Rating of the Respondents on the Level of Public Secondary Social Science Teachers in terms of Managing Behavior

Nomenclature	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Level of Self-efficacy
I am confident in my ability to prevent disruptive behavior in the classroom before it occurs.	3.60	0.56	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy
I can control disruptive behavior in the classroom	3.63	0.58	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy
I am able to calm a student who is disruptive or noisy	3.61	0.58	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy
I am able to get students to follow classroom rules	3.69	0.56	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy
I am confident when dealing with students who are physically aggressive	3.45	0.67	Agree	High Self-efficacy
I can make my expectations clear about student behavior	3.60	0.56	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy
Weighted Mean	3.60	0.58	Strongly Agree	High Self-efficacy

Table 6 presents that the respondents obtained a mean of 3.60, implying that the teachers have high self-efficacy in terms of managing behavior. Further, teachers can adeptly manage classroom behavior, cultivating a confident and efficient teaching environment. They are inclined to employ proactive strategies, handle challenges calmly, and nurture positive teacher-student relationships. In consequence, this cultivates a conducive learning atmosphere that significantly influences pivotal academic outcomes, including students' learning behavior, and contributes to overall well-being in the workplace.

Moreover, they are more expected to have efficacy in classroom behavior management, which comprises a major part of teachers' self-efficacy in a mainstream classroom, leading to improved student learning behavior (Kundu, 2021).

Significant Difference between the Level of Self-Efficacy of Public Secondary Social Science Teachers across Profile Variables as to Grade Level Handled; Teaching Position; and Years in Service

This section presents the significant difference between the level of self-efficacy of public secondary social science teachers across profile variables as to grade level handled; teaching position; and years in service.

Significant Difference between the Level of Self-Efficacy of Public Secondary Social Science Teachers and Grade Level Handled

Table 7 shows the self-efficacy in fostering inclusive education grouped by grade level handled. It can be noted from the table that there is no significant difference between the levels of teacher's self-efficacy i.e. between groups and grade level handled i.e. within the groups based on the f-value of 0.399 with the corresponding probability value of 0.848, which is greater than alpha 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

In connection, Masongsong, et.al (2023) found out in their study that the teachers' self-efficacy in instructional strategies differed significantly based on age and years of teaching specifically at the elementary level. Whereas, in this study, the results showed that there is no significant difference between the level of public secondary social science teachers in the junior and senior high school levels. It can be concluded that young learners are more likely to be influenced by teachers' level of self-efficacy than with the higher levels.

Table 7. Test of Significant Difference on the Level Public Secondary Social Science Teachers and Grade Level Handled Variables using One-way ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision	Interpretation
Between Groups	0.396	5	0.079				
Within Groups	15.473	78	0.198	0.399	0.848	Do not Reject Ho	No significant Difference
Total	15.869	83					

α=0.5 level of significance

Significant Difference between the Level of Self-Efficacy of Public Secondary Social Science Teachers and Teaching Position

Table 8 shows the self-efficacy in fostering inclusive education grouped by teaching position. It can be gathered from the table that there is no significant difference between the levels of teachers' self-efficacy i.e. between groups and teaching position i.e. within the groups based on the f-value of 1.763 with the corresponding probability value of 0.145 which is greater than alpha 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 8. Test of Significant Difference on the Level of Public Secondary Social Science Teachers and Years in Service Variables using One-way ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision	Interpretation
Between Groups	1.3	4	0.325				
Within Groups	14.569	79	0.184	1.763	0.145	Do not Reject Ho	No significant Difference
Total	15.869	83					

α=0.5 level of significance

In addition, Emmer et al. (2019) found out that teachers in higher education generally possess moderate positive attitudes and self-efficacy toward inclusive education. However, they also suggest that policy reforms should prioritize the provision of more role models for disabled students and practical training experiences for teachers in inclusive education. In contrast, the result of this study revealed that the level of self-efficacy among public secondary social science teachers remains consistent regardless of their teaching position.

This suggests that teaching positions may not significantly impact self-efficacy levels in this context. Overall, while higher education teachers may benefit from additional support and training, public secondary social science teachers seem to maintain a consistent level of self-efficacy across different teaching positions.

Significant Difference between the Level of Self-Efficacy of Public Secondary Social Science Teachers and Years in Service

Table 9 shows the self-efficacy in fostering inclusive education Grouped by years in service. It can be gathered from the table that there is no significant difference between the levels of teachers self-efficacy i.e. between groups and years in service i.e. within groups based on the f-value of 0.627 with the corresponding probability value of 0.645 which is greater than alpha 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Furthermore, in the study of Geleta (2019), focusing on public school teachers in general, concluded that there was no significant discrepancy between self-efficacy levels and teaching experience in the realm of inclusive education. Similarly, the result of the study, which specifically targeted public social science teachers, yielded a parallel finding, indicating that there was no notable distinction between the self-efficacy levels of these teachers and their years of teaching experience in fostering inclusive education. These consistent results across different subsets of teachers suggest that regardless of specialization or broader teaching context, years in service do not significantly impact self- efficacy levels concerning inclusive education.

Table 9. *Significant Difference between the Level of Self-Efficacy of Public Secondary Social Science Teachers and Years in Service*

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision	Interpretation
Between Groups	0.488	4	0.122				
Within Groups	15.381	79	0.195	0.627	0.645	Do not Reject Ho	No significant Difference
Total	15.869	83					

$\alpha=0.5$ level of significance

Concerns Encountered by the Public secondary social science teachers in Fostering Inclusive Education

This section presents the concerns the public secondary social science teachers encounter in fostering inclusive education in terms of resources; difficulties; appropriateness; and workload.

Resources

Table 10 shows the concerns encountered by the public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education are evident in the data. The highest mean, with a score of 3.13 and a standard deviation of 0.71, is associated with the worry that schools may lack sufficient funds for the successful implementation of inclusive education. Additionally, teachers express a significant level of concern, as indicated using 3.01 (SD:0.87) and 3.05 (SD: 0.88), about the potential inadequacy of para-professional staff and resources/substitute teacher staff to support students with diverse learning needs. The overall weighted mean, combining these concerns, is 3.06 with a standard deviation of 0.82, highlighting that, on average, public secondary social science teachers are very concerned about the challenges linked to fostering inclusive education. Addressing these apprehensions is crucial for creating an environment conducive to successful inclusive education practices.

Table 10. *Concerns encountered by the Public Secondary Social Science Teachers in Terms of Resources*

Nomenclature	Mean	SD	Interpretation
My school will not have enough funds to implement inclusive education successfully	3.13	0.71	Very Concerned
There will be inadequate para-professional staff available to support students with different learning needs	3.01	0.87	Very Concerned
There will be inadequate resources/substitute teacher staff available to support inclusive education	3.05	0.88	Very Concerned
Weighted Mean	3.06	0.82	Very Concerned

Moreover, the study by Sanchez et al. (2019) found out that future education professionals identify various barriers to inclusive learning, including insufficient teacher training, lack of diversity, and underutilization of resources within educational centers. Conversely, the findings of this study reveal that public secondary social science teachers express significant concerns about the challenges associated with fostering inclusive education, particularly regarding funding shortages within their schools for implementing inclusive education

practices. Addressing these challenges, especially funding constraints, is essential to effectively promote inclusive education within schools. In conclusion, both studies emphasize the importance of addressing perceived barriers and challenges to create an environment conducive to successful inclusive education practices.

Difficulties

Based on the results of the data in table 11 shows that public secondary social science teachers express substantial concerns regarding the implementation of inclusive education, as evidenced in the data reflecting encountered difficulties. With a mean score of 2.54 (SD: 0.97), there is unease about maintaining discipline in an inclusive classroom. Similarly, providing equal attention to all students in such a context is a significant concern, with a mean score of 2.60 (SD: 0.89). Moreover, teachers express worry about the potential rise in anxiety and stress levels when incorporating a student with diverse learning needs into their class, indicated by a mean score of 2.56 (SD: 0.94). The overall weighted mean, combining these challenges, is 2.56 with a standard deviation of 0.93, emphasizing that, on average, public secondary social science teachers harbor substantial concerns about the obstacles associated with fostering inclusive education. Addressing these concerns is imperative for establishing an inclusive environment that effectively supports both teachers and students.

Moreover, the study of Jardi et al. (2021) found out that in inclusive Catalan schools, both teaching assistants and teachers effectively handle disruptive behavior by employing shared proactive and reactive strategies, highlighting the significance of having multiple adults present in a classroom. Conversely, the result of this study revealed that public social science teachers express considerable concerns regarding the challenge of maintaining discipline in an inclusive classroom setting. These findings underscore the importance of addressing concerns related to classroom management in inclusive settings, particularly among social science teachers. In conclusion, while collaborative strategies prove effective in managing disruptive behavior in inclusive classrooms, it is essential to address teachers' apprehensions and provide support to ensure the successful implementation of inclusive education practices.

Table 11. *Concerns encountered by the Public Secondary Social Science Teachers in Terms of Difficulties*

Nomenclature	Mean	SD	Interpretation
It will be difficult to maintain discipline in class	2.54	0.97	Very Concerned
It will be difficult to give equal attention to all students in an inclusive classroom	2.60	0.89	Very Concerned
The inclusion of a student with diverse learning needs in my class will lead higher degree of anxiety and stress in me	2.56	0.94	Very Concerned
Weighted Mean	2.56	0.93	Very Concerned

Appropriateness

Table 12 shows that the Public secondary social science teachers are notably concerned about the appropriateness of implementing inclusive education, as evidenced by the data. Their primary worry centers around the possible adverse effects on the overall academic standard of the school, reflected in a mean score of 2.73. Although there is still apprehension regarding the impact on classroom teachers' performance, indicated by a mean score of 2.48, it is comparatively less pronounced.

Table 12. *Concerns encountered by the Public Secondary Social Science Teachers in Terms of Appropriateness*

Nomenclature	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The overall academic standard of the school will suffer	2.73	0.95	Very Concerned
My performance as a classroom teacher will decline	2.48	1.10	A Little Concerned
The academic achievement of students without learning difficulties will be affected	2.74	0.97	Very Concerned
Weighted Mean	2.65	1.01	Very Concerned

Additionally, significant concern exists about the potential impact on the academic achievement of students without learning difficulties, with a mean score of 2.74. The aggregated weighted mean for these appropriateness concerns is 2.65, with a standard deviation of 1.01, highlighting that, on average, public secondary social science teachers possess substantial concerns about the

challenges associated with fostering inclusive education. Addressing these concerns is imperative to establish an inclusive environment that aligns with academic standards while catering to the needs of all students.

In connection, the study by Möller et.al (2021) on inclusive education positively impacts cognitive outcomes (e.g., academic performance) for students with general learning difficulties, but not psychosocial outcomes (e.g., self-concept, well-being), while students without learning difficulties show no significant difference. On the other hand, the result of this study showed that public secondary social science teachers worry a lot about how to keep up with academic standards while making classrooms inclusive. It is important to deal with these worries so that inclusive education can meet academic standards and help all students succeed. Working together with teachers, school leaders, and policymakers is key to making inclusive education work well for everyone.

Workload

Delving deeper into the survey data. Table 13 indicates that public social science educators express substantial apprehensions regarding the impact of workload in promoting inclusive education. With an average score of 2.70 (SD: 0.97), there is heightened concern about the inadequate time available to plan educational programs for students with diverse learning needs. Similarly, the worry is notably significant (mean score: 2.64, SD: 1.00) concerning perceived insufficiencies in incentives, such as additional remuneration, for teaching students with diverse learning needs.

Additionally, teachers express considerable anxiety about the potential workload increase associated with fostering inclusive education, as evidenced by a mean score of 2.64 (SD: 1.03). The overall weighted mean for these workload concerns is 2.74 with a standard deviation of 0.94, indicating that, on average, public secondary social science teachers possess significant concerns regarding workload challenges in the context of fostering inclusive education. Addressing these concerns is crucial to ensuring educators can effectively meet the diverse needs of their students.

According to the study of Akbar et.al (2023), the importance of differentiated instruction is tailored to individual learning styles and abilities. Teachers implementing flexible teaching methods reported improved engagement and understanding among diverse learners.

However, the findings of this study reveal significant concerns among public social science educators about workload. These concerns make it difficult for teachers to create effective educational plans for students. In conclusion, while personalized instruction has been shown to benefit diverse learners, addressing workload concerns is crucial to ensure that teachers can implement these strategies effectively and support the varied needs of their students.

Table 13. *Concerns encountered by the Public Secondary Social Science Teachers in Terms of Workload*

Nomenclature	Mean	SD	Interpretation
I will not have enough time to plan educational programs for students with diverse learning need	2.70	0.97	Very Concerned
I will not receive enough incentives (e.g., additional remuneration to teach students with diverse learning needs	2.64	1.00	Very Concerned
My workload will increase	2.64	1.03	Very Concerned
Weighted Mean	2.74	0.94	Very Concerned

Qualitative Phase

The sequential QUAN QUAL analysis methodology calls for the identification of a group of individuals who were similar to one another for the qualitative phase. The researcher followed the systematic process by Creswell (2007) for the analysis of qualitative data. The process commenced by meticulously transcribing the interviews with key informants, followed by the identification of meaning units through an open coding procedure to discern categories and condense the meaning units. This process was used to extract the key informants about the challenges they encountered in fostering inclusive education to propose a well-developed program on inclusive education.

Key Informants. In determining the key informants for this study, the researcher set these three (3) significant and relevant criteria: (1) someone who holds a key role in understanding diversity and inclusion principles and practices, (2) someone who has demonstrated inclusive education practices in the performance of his / her responsibilities, and (3) someone who possesses strong communication and collaboration skills, enabling them to effectively engage with diverse stakeholders, including students, staff, families, and community members.

In consultation with the research adviser and upon a deeper look at the profile, the 5 key informants, based on their profile, fitted very well with the criteria.

The researcher compiled a shortlist of five candidates who met the predetermined criteria. Table 14 provides a summary of these candidates' profiles, including their positions within the school and the reasons why they met the qualifications.

Table 14. Profile of All Qualifiers as Key Informants of the Study

QUALIFIER	POSITION	PROFILE
1	School Principal	He collaborates with teachers, staff, students, families, and community members to develop and implement initiatives that promote inclusivity and address systemic barriers to learning.
2	Social Science teacher	She integrates diverse perspectives and experiences into their curriculum, creating opportunities for all students to see themselves reflected in the material.
3	Master teacher in Social Science Department	She provides support and guidance to fellow teachers in implementing inclusive practices, designing curriculum modifications, and creating a welcoming classroom environment for all students.
4	School Guidance Counselor	She serves as an advocate for students, ensuring that their individual needs are met and that they have access to the necessary support systems to thrive academically, socially, and emotionally.
5	Special Education teacher in Social Science	He develops and implements individualized education plans (IEPs) for students with disabilities in social science classes. They modify curriculum materials, assessments, and instructional strategies to meet the unique needs of each student.

In consultation with the research adviser and upon a deeper look at the profile, the 5 key informants, based on their profile, fitted very well with the criteria.

Interviews with Key Informants. All the five final key informants were asked to sign a consent form for the interview. Appointments were made, the interviews were conducted, and audio recorded for the transcription.

Analysis of the Interview. Involved formulating meaning units and condensing them into categories, which were then coded to identify emergent themes. These themes were labeled meticulously and accurately to maintain the essence of the described phenomenon, following the guidelines outlined in Colaizzi's method.

Emerging Theme 1

Table 15. Summary of Themes Derived from the Meaning Unit, Condensed Meaning Unit, and Subthemes that Surfaced from the Interview with Key Informants

MEANING UNIT	CONDENSED MEANING UNIT	SUB-THEMES	THEME
<i>"...one challenge is addressing the diverse learning needs of our students. We have students with varying abilities, learning styles, and socio-economic backgrounds, which requires us to tailor our teaching approaches to meet individual needs."</i>	Teaching methods to accommodate diverse student abilities, learning styles, and socio-economic backgrounds.	Inclusive Instruction	Teaching Practices for Student Success
<i>"assessing how well students are learning can be tough. The usual ways we test might not show how every student is doing because everyone learns differently..."</i>	Challenges in assessing student learning due to diverse learning styles necessitate finding new, equitable methods to monitor progress and ensure inclusivity.	Responsive Teaching Practices	
<i>"...we don't have a lot of time or things to work with in class. Sometimes there's not enough materials or extra help. It makes it hard to help every student in the way they need because everyone learns differently."</i>	Limited time and resources hinder individualized support for diverse learning needs	Time Management	
<i>"...I have to try to help each student learn in a way that works best for them, so they can understand and be involved in what we're learning."</i>	Customizing learning for each student's comprehension and engagement.	Differentiated Instruction	
<i>"...sometimes, we don't have enough money or extra help in our school. This can make it hard for me as a social studies teacher to use different ways of teaching that could help all students learn better..."</i>	Limited resources hinder the implementation of diverse teaching methods, impacting student learning.	Innovative Solutions	

Emerging Theme 2

Table 16. Summary of Themes Derived from the Meaning Unit, Condensed Meaning Unit, and Subthemes that Surfaced from the Interview with Key Informants

<i>MEANING UNIT</i>	<i>CONDENSED MEANING UNIT</i>	<i>SUB-THEMES</i>	<i>THEME</i>
<p>“...some are very active, some are quiet, and some may sometimes act out. I have to figure out how to help each student behave well and focus on learning, which can be a bit tricky because everyone is different.”</p> <p>“...sometimes, things can get a bit crazy in our classroom. Students might interrupt, not focus on their work, or argue with each other.”</p> <p>“...we might not have paraprofessionals or special programs to support students who need extra help with their behavior.”</p> <p>“...this can make it tough for me to handle some behavior problems in class. It would be easier if we had more support to help us deal with these challenges.”</p> <p>“In our school, sometimes we don't have enough help to manage behavior issues. This can make it difficult for teachers like me to handle challenging behaviors on our own, and it can feel overwhelming at times.”</p>	<p>Strive to manage diverse student behaviors to promote engagement and learning, recognizing individual differences.</p> <p>To maintain a conducive learning environment amidst potential disruptions, ensuring all students can engage effectively.</p> <p>Lack of support personnel or specialized programs for students requiring behavioral assistance</p> <p>Limited support exacerbates challenges in managing behavior in class.</p> <p>Limited support for behavior management can overwhelm teachers, hindering the effective handling of challenging behaviors.</p>	<p>Classroom Behavior Management</p> <p>Classroom Management and Engagement</p> <p>Resource Constraints in Behavior Support</p> <p>Lack of support services</p> <p>Lack of support services</p>	<p><i>Classroom-limited environments for positive behavior and student support</i></p>

Emerging Theme 3

Table 17. Summary of Themes Derived from the Meaning Unit, Condensed Meaning Unit, and Subthemes that Surfaced from the Interview with Key Informants

<i>MEANING UNIT</i>	<i>CONDENSED MEANING UNIT</i>	<i>SUB-THEMES</i>	<i>THEME</i>
<p>“...it can be hard for social science teachers to work together because we're all so busy with different things. We might not have much time to meet or talk about how to make our classes better for everyone.”</p> <p>“...the way things are set up in our school can make it hard for social science teachers to work together. There might be a lot of rules or priorities from the administration that get in the way.”</p> <p>“It's hard for us to make sure everyone can learn together. We need more support and training to do this well.”</p>	<p>Limited collaboration among social science teachers due to busy schedules hinders opportunities for improving class quality collectively.</p> <p>Administrative barriers impede collaboration among social science teachers, hindering effective teamwork.</p> <p>Struggle to ensure inclusive learning for all and require additional support and training to excel in this endeavor.</p>	<p>Institutional Barriers</p> <p>Limited training and professional development</p> <p>Limited training and professional development</p>	<p><i>Limited training and Professional Development</i></p>

<p>“...some classrooms have too many students and not enough teachers. This makes it hard for the teacher to help everyone because there are so many students to look after.”</p> <p>“...dealing with the rules and paperwork from the DepEd can be tough. Sometimes, it makes it hard for me as a social science teacher to do what’s best for all my students.”</p>	<p>Limited teacher-to-student ratio in overcrowded classrooms hampers individualized student support and attention. Overcrowded classrooms limit individualized student support due to low teacher-to-student ratios.</p>	<p>Overcrowded Classrooms</p> <p>Bureaucratic Challenges</p>
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Integration of QUAN QUAL Data: After analyzing the data from both the quantitative (Teacher Efficacy for Inclusive Practice (TEIP) and Concerns about Inclusive Education Scale – Short Form (CIES-SF) Survey and qualitative (Interview with Key Informants) methods, they were integrated to finalize and derive the key priorities for the proposed development program. Table 1.4 presents the integration of the highest-rated concerns from the survey and the themes derived from the interview. The three key priorities based on the integration are as follows: (1) Optimizing teaching practices for student success, (2) Upgrade training and professional development for public secondary social science teachers, and (3) Sustaining classroom environments for positive behavior and student support. These key priorities served as the main considerations in developing a proposed program aimed at empowering public secondary social science teachers to foster inclusive education through the enhancement of 21st-century pedagogies.

These key priorities served as the primary considerations in developing the proposed program.

Table 18. *Integration of the Quantitative and Qualitative Data Analysis on the level of self- efficacy of public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education at the standards/Key Priority Areas*

QUANTITATIVE Highest rated concerns	QUALITATIVE Themes derived from the interview	INTEGRATED THEME Standards/ Key Priorities
It will be difficult to maintain discipline in class	Teaching Practices for Student Success	Optimizing teaching practices for student success
I will not have enough time to plan educational programs for students with diverse learning need	Limited training and Professional Development	Upgrade training and professional development for public secondary social science teachers
There will be inadequate resources/substitute teacher staff available to support inclusive education	Classroom- limited environments for positive behavior and student support	Sustaining classroom environments for positive behavior and student support.

Empowering the Public Secondary Social Science Teachers in Fostering Inclusive Education Through Enhancement of 21st-Century Pedagogies. Based on the integration of QUAN QUAL analysis, a program matrix is presented in table 17. The figure illustrates the three key priorities of empowering the public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education through the enhancement of 21st-century pedagogies as follows: (1) Optimizing teaching practices for student success, (2) Upgrade training and professional development for public secondary social science teachers, and (3) Sustaining classroom environments for positive behavior and student support. These key priorities were the key considerations that were used in developing the proposed program to foster inclusive education.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were made based on the result of the problem:

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn: Firstly, the study found that most participants were from the "grade 9 level" bracket. Secondly, in terms of teaching positions, most participants held the position of "Teacher I". Finally, the study revealed that most participants had less than five years of teaching experience. The level of self-efficacy of public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education in terms of inclusive instruction, collaboration, and managing behavior was "High Self-efficacy." This shows that public secondary social science teachers are skilled at handling their tasks and challenges, which helps improve student achievement and motivation. They can confidently engage students, and manage classroom behavior, to build positive relationships.

The survey results also revealed no significant difference in the level of self-efficacy among public secondary social science teachers across profile variables such as grade level handled, teaching position, and years of service. This further implies that the level of self-efficacy of public secondary social science teachers in terms of inclusive practices, collaboration, and managing behavior is the same regardless of the profile variables. The teachers' grade level handled, teaching position, and number of years in service have nothing to do with their level of self-efficacy. In this case, the study's choice to reject the null hypothesis was deemed unsuccessful. It demonstrates that no matter the teachers' backgrounds, it has no effect on or has anything to do with their level of self-efficacy.

Based on the survey results, most of the public secondary social science teachers encountered concerns in fostering inclusive education related to learners lacking the ability to maintain discipline inside the classroom, teachers not having enough time to plan for educational programs for students with diverse learning needs, and inadequate resources/substitute teacher staff available to support inclusive education. Teachers who took part in answering the survey questions had the opportunity to rate their related concerns regarding resources, difficulties, appropriateness, and workload.

In another layer of the study, the three standards or key priority areas to enhance the challenges of public secondary social science teachers in fostering inclusive education are as follows: (1) optimizing teaching practices for student success, (2) Sustaining classroom environments for positive behavior and student support, and (3) Upgrade training and professional development. Even when the overall levels of self-efficacy among public secondary social science teachers have not shown a significant impact across their profile variables significant areas of challenges and concerns have largely surfaced. These are believed to further enhance their level of self-efficacy in fostering inclusive education in the social science classroom.

A program designed to address the challenges encountered by the public social science teachers gathered from this study is a suitable solution and it would help in incorporating inclusive practices within and among public secondary social science classrooms.

The following recommendations were proposed based on the findings of the study:

That, it is recommended other teachers' profile should be evaluated for their level of self-efficacy in fostering inclusive education. A future study may look at whether the other personality characteristic has anything to do with their inclusive practices, such as the educational background, number of trainings attended, and gender.

That, the different strategies outlined in the proposed program undergo an evaluation to assess their strengths and areas for improvement following each implementation. Furthermore, it is recommended that a follow-up study be conducted to assess the effectiveness of the program in promoting inclusive education within the social science classroom. Based on the findings, adjustments to the program should be made as necessary.

That, public secondary social science educators should actively participate in continuous training sessions to better understand and support the diverse requirements of their students to improve and meet their concerns and challenges in fostering inclusive education.

That, the education sector in the Philippines should provide opportunities for public secondary social science teachers to receive ongoing training and support in fostering inclusive education. This will broaden the adoption of inclusive practices and ensure a balanced inclusive education culture throughout the school.

That, future researchers related to this present one should be conducted to expand the pool of respondents by involving other stakeholders such as students and parents.

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